

Application of Re-writing Algorithm for Assertions in Regular Expressions

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ABSTRACT

We give the linear algorithm for re-writing negative and positive lookaheads and lookbehinds in modern regular expressions.

Keywords: algorithm, assertion, regular expression.

INTRODUCTION

The assertions is a modern trend in regular expressions [1-4], we use the re-writing technique for our set algebra with extended operators like intersection, subtraction and complement which is linear in complexity $O(n*m)$ [5].

RE-WRITING ALGORITHM

Thus, we have the following statements for any assertion and extended operators:

$$\begin{aligned} (?=<a>)[] &= (<a>.* & ()), \\ (?!<a>)[] &= () - (<a>.*). \end{aligned}$$

Same is true for look-behind assertions:

$$\begin{aligned} [](?<=<a>) &= (. *<a>)& (), \\ [](?!<a>) &= () - (. *<a>). \end{aligned}$$

CONCLUSION

We have made a step forward in exploring the set algebra for extended regular expressions.

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